

Mothers of Hospitalized Children's Perspectives on Male Nurses Care

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 14, 2021

Accepted:
June 24, 2021

Keywords :

Children, Nurses, Male,
Jordan

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5026759

Abstract

Many professions have been categorized by gender until recently. Various societies and businesses have differing views on whether particular jobs required men or women to succeed. Males are viewed as model leaders in both the health care system and the larger society. Men are regarded as self-assured and assertive. On the other hand, female nurses are seen as compassionate by health professionals and the general public. Today, these views, including Jordan's, have shifted in different parts of the world. This descriptive study aimed to learn about the viewpoints of mothers whose children were in-patients receiving hospital care on male nurses. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted; 220 mothers of hospitalized children of varying ages, educational levels, work status, residency, & income status were recruited using random sampling techniques. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences to generate descriptive and inferential statistics with the level of significance set at 0.05. 35% stated that nursing was not a job only for women, while 68% stated that male nurses should be in healthcare. In addition, 49% of the mothers who participated in the research indicated that male nurses should look after male patients, and 15% indicated that there should not be gender discrimination in nursing occupations. When asked about the duties of male nurses, 10% stated that they treated patients. There was a statistically significant difference between all sociodemographic characteristics of mothers and their perspectives about male nurses working. It was concluded that mothers had favorable attitudes toward male nurses.

Introduction

Many professions are still being categorized by gender until recently. Societies and enterprises had several assumptions as to whether some professions needed male or female qualifications to fulfill them. The healthcare system and the general population see males as prototypical leaders. Men are perceived to be assertive and to have a sense of dominance. On the other hand, female nurses are seen as compassionate and supportive by health care officials and the general population. These views have to some degree shifted nowadays worldwide, including Jordanian society.

Although nursing maintains to be mainly a female-dominated profession (Haigh, 2015), an ever-changing health sector tends to redefine the nurse's position by increasing the number of men joining the nursing profession as they see it for reasons of economic opportunity. However, men have difficulties in getting their nursing roles accepted by society. Although some studies have shown that clients prefer male nurses (Ahmad & Alasad, 2007), other research provided reasons that influence the misconception which reinforces that men are unfit for nursing (Adeyemi-Adelanwa, Barton, Dawkins, & Lindo, 2015), such as negative stereotypes, where the nurse has been labeled as gay, power-hungry and lazy (Genua, 2005) and the reference to the nurse as "she" in the nursing discourse (Hodes, 2005; Grady, Stewardson & Hall, 2008).

Men in the nursing face many hurdles from the community and their clients and their families. The media's biased depiction of male nurses and society's cultural orientation regarding males' unsuitability to deliver treatment have the potential to influence the psychological orientation of male nurses who experience elevated levels of anxiety and stress on the job (Sochalsk, 2002; Armour, 2003; Lou, Yu, Hsu, & Dai, 2007). In the case where these causes aren't present, male nurses are thought to be treated differently.

Although men have recently regarded nursing as a desired profession for various reasons (Evans, 2004; Ahmad & Alasad, 2007; Yi & Keogh, 2016), conflicting emotions about clients' encounters with male nurses continue to exist. Clients rated their happiness with male nurses in some surveys (Younas & Sundus, 2018), while others viewed care as a trait of female nurses, implying a noncaring picture of male nurses (O'Lynn, 2007; Zamanzadeh, Valizadeh, Negarandeh, Monadi & Azadi, 2013). In addition, inconsistent studies have been published on client opinion and satisfaction with treatment rendered by male nurses, both within the same country (Ekstrom, 1999) and across countries (Adeyemi-Adelanwa et al., 2015; Younas & Sundus, 2018). The presence of these inconsistencies continues to breed confounding evidence on clients' preference for, general

orientation towards, and acceptability of males, as nurses (Hood, 2002; Harding, 2007). These mixed reactions and contradictions around clients' preferences for, and satisfaction of, male nurses' treatment (Ekstrom, 1999; Ahmad & Alasad, 2007; O'Lynn, 2007; Zamanzadeh et al., 2013; Adeyemi-Adelanwa et al., 2015; Younas & Sundus, 2018) call for further research to resolve these gaps.

Despite the discrepancies shown in both developing and low-and middle-income countries, a survey on clients' and their carers' preferences for, and satisfaction of, nursing care provided by male nurses is yet to be conducted in Jordan. Therefore, the primary goal of this study was to determine mothers' preferences with the treatment given by male nurses at the Queen Rania Al Abdullah Hospital for Children as caregivers to their hospitalized children.

Having evidence of the beliefs and attitudes of clients and their carers regarding the gender of their nurses can be invaluable in enabling nurses to perform care that preserves dignity, as well as being safe, compassionate, competent, and ethical.

Research Questions

1. What are Jordanian mothers' perspectives on male nurses caring for their children?
2. Do the sociodemographic characteristics of the mothers influence their perspectives toward male nursing?

Study Objective

Given the males' derogatory mark of nursing and the social-cultural orientation towards male nurses, this research visualizes possibly facilitating or inhibiting the choice of health clients and the satisfactory use of nursing services by male nurses in the case of mothers of hospitalized children's demographic features.

It is widely assumed in the Jordanian culture that the caregiver is usually a female, especially in the maternity and pediatrics wards, mothers' perspectives on male nurses will vary.

Hence, this study aims to learn about mothers' perspectives on the health care provided to their hospitalized children by male nurses.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional approach has been conducted from the 7th of January to the 27th of February 2021 as it is thought to be compatible with the objectives of this study.

Procedure & Method

Participants were told about the study before data collection and that their participation was free and anonymous.

Informed consent was obtained from everyone accepted to participate. Of the 240 mothers who approached, 220 agreed and took part in the study, which provided a survey response rate of 91.6% for the study.

Data were collected from early January to the end of February 2021. The research tools used do not contain a personal identification code but are directly handled and collected by the researcher, preventing other individuals (such as hospital department managers) from observing the individually filled-out forms. The questionnaires were obtained from the respondents and returned to the researcher after completion.

Participants & Sampling

Random sampling has been applied to select participants (n = 220) from departments providing direct client care in the Queen Rania Al Abdullah Hospital for Children in Amman who agreed to participate in the study (Table 1) excluded from the sample mothers who have disagreed to participate or withdraw.

Measurement

To collect the required data for the study, we used a questionnaire that was originally developed by Korkmaz, Büyük, & rızalar (2015). A set of 14 items were selected to generate preliminary items of the instrument.

In the first part of the questionnaire, sociodemographic data, the questionnaire includes 14 questions about the mothers' sociodemographic features and their views on nursing and male nurses.

Instrument Validity

To validate the study questionnaire and ensure its suitability to the Jordanian culture and to ensure its usability, it was presented to a panel of experts in the nursing field.

The experts evaluated the content validity index of the questionnaire. They were asked to assess the items related to the objectives and provide a critique of the questionnaire. Finally, the experts determined the suitability of the questionnaire for this study.

The revised questionnaire consisted of two sections A & B. Section A is designed to gather participants' demographic data, while section B is designed to gather mothers' thoughts and views about male nurses providing health care to their hospitalized children.

Reliability

The reliability of the study was checked throughout a test implementing on 30 mothers from outside the study's sample, with a time difference of two weeks. After collecting data and analyzing mothers' responses, the Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.88, which is acceptable for the current study.

Data Analysis

The number, percentage, Pearson, and Fisher chi-square tests were analyzed using SPSS 15.0 packaged software. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Limitations

The study failed to examine mothers' opinions on specific intimate care services they will or will not permit male nurses to perform on their children. Given that age, educational level, work status, residency, & income status significantly predicted mothers' perspectives on male nurses caring for their children, including such specifics (type of care) would have helped reveal other salient patterns. Significantly too, though this study argued on the homogeneity of the study sample and the generalisability of the study findings, it ought to be considered with caution due to the vulnerability of convenience sampling to some hidden biases.

Demographic Characteristics

In section A of the questionnaire, the questions were concerned with collecting sociodemographic data from participants to determine whether the participants were a homogenous or heterogeneous group of Jordanian mothers in terms of several factors. These factors were age (less than 30 years of age, between 31-40 years of age, over 41 years of age), educational level (Illiterate, primary school, secondary school, high school-university), work status (housewife, has a job), residency (city, town, village), & income status (expense than income, equal income, and expense, more income than expense) as it shown in Table (1) below.

The sociodemographic data provides an overview of the Jordanian mothers who agreed to participate because they had a particular interest in the study area or who considered they could significantly contribute to the topic in this study.

Table 1. The demographics

Characteristics	Variables	Number	Percentage
Age	Less than 30 years of age	33	26.6%
	Between 31-40 years of age	71	62%
	Over 41 years of age	20	16%
Educational Level	Illiterate	11	9%
	Primary school	25	20%
	Secondary school	32	26%
	High school- university	56	45%
Work Status	Housewife	58	47%
	Has a job	66	53%
Residency	Urban	60	48%
	Rural	64	52%
Income Status	300 JD or less	26	21%
	301 JD - 600 JD	78	63%
	601 JD or more	20	16%
Total		124	100%

62% of the mothers were between 31-40 years of age, 45% were high school/university graduates, and 66% has a job. Another 52% of the mothers lived in rural areas, incomes and expenses of 63% ranged between 301 JD - 600 JD (Table 1).

Results of the Study

To answer the first question:

(What are Jordanian mothers' perspectives on male nurses caring for their children?)

The frequency and percentage of the participant's responses on the questionnaire items were calculated, and the results are shown below in table 2.

Table 2. Mothers' perspectives on male nurses

Variable		Frequency (n=124)	Percent (%)
Is nursing a job for women?	Yes	81	65%
	No	43	35%
Should there be male nurses?	Yes	84	68%
	No	40	32%
If your answer is yes, why?	There should not be gender discrimination	18	15%
	Because it is a difficult job	32	26%
	To look after male patients	61	49%
	No answer	13	10%
If your answer is no, why?	Because it is a job for women	56	45%
	Because it doesn't suit men	25	20%
	Yes answer	43	35%
What are the duties of a nurse?	Checking vital signs & Treatment	88	71%
	Checking vital signs & Wound dressing	16	13%
	Checking vital signs & Blood samples withdrawal	14	11%
	All	6	5%
What are the duties of male nurses?	Checking vital signs + treatment	82	66%
	All	30	24%
	Treatment	12	10%
Did you know that male nurses are also working in a hospital?	Yes	90	73%
	No	34	27%
Where did you learn that male nurses are working in a hospital?	when I came to the hospital	68	55%
	friend+relative+family	34	27%
	TV+internet+media	22	18%
Total		124	100%

Nursing is not a job only for women; 65% of the mothers and 68% believe male nurses should work in healthcare. In addition, 49% of the mothers who took part in the survey said there should be male nurses to look after male patients, 26% said men should also take nursing jobs because it's difficult to work, and 15% said that gender discrimination should not occur in nursing. Of the mothers who felt there should not be male nurses, 45% claimed that nursing is a work for women, and 20% said nursing isn't suitable for men.

When mothers were asked what nurses' duties were, 71% said monitoring vital signs and treatment.

However, when the mothers were asked what male nurses' duties were, 66% stated that they checked vital signs and treated patients, 10% stated that they treated patients, and 24% stated that they did everything.

73% of the mothers said they were aware of male nurses serving in hospitals. In addition, 55% of mothers said they knew about male nurses as they visited the hospital, 27% said they learned from friends and family, and 18% said they heard about male nurses from TV, newspapers, and the internet.

To answer the second question: (Do the sociodemographic characteristics of the mothers influence their perspectives toward male nursing?) the means and standard deviations were statistically calculated for the variables of age, educational level, work status, residency, income status, & family type as shown in table 3 below.

Table 3. The association between sociodemographic characteristics of the mothers and their perspectives on male nurses

Characteristics	Variables	Yes		No		X ² ,p
		n	%	N	%	
Age	Less than 30 years of age	24	19%	12	10%	8.31*
	Between 31-40 years of age	60	50%	14	11%	0.05

Educational Level	Over 41 years of age	6	5%	8	6%	
	Illiterate	10	8%	8	7%	7.11*
	Primary school	30	24%	13	10%	0.05
	Secondary school	20	16%	10	8%	
Work Status	High school- university	26	21%	7	6%	
	Housewife	71	57%	18	15%	13.06*
Residency	Has a job	25	20%	10	8%	0.05
	Urban	78	63%	15	12%	14.06*
Income Status	Rural	18	15%	13	10%	0.05
	300 JD or less	16	13%	8	7%	7.70*
	301 JD - 600 JD	40	32%	15	12%	0.05
	601 JD or more	30	24%	15	12%	

*Pearson Chi-Square

Table 3 shows that statistically significant associations were found between mothers' sociodemographic characteristics and their perspectives on male nurses ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Discussion of the Results

This study is the first to explore Jordanian mothers' perspectives on nursing care provided by male nurses to their children. Respondents' perspectives on and satisfaction with male nursing care were functions of their age, educational level, work status, residency, & income status.

Although men are not perceived or portrayed as natural caregivers, they seem to be doing well in the nursing field, based on client perceptions (Budu et al., 2019).

Male nurses, according to the mothers who took part in this survey, should work in healthcare. Thus, positive approval of male nurses in this sample may indicate a positive outlook and professional conduct on the part of male nurses and widespread acceptance of male nurses, cultural heterogeneity among study participants.

The current research results are comparable with the findings of Achora (2016), who reported that male nurses are approachable, courteous, and do create an environment conducive for their patients, as well as Adeyemi-Adelanwa et al. (2015) & Sundus and Younas (2020).

Although current research results consistent with previous research suggesting that clients were comfortable with nursing care regardless of the nurses' gender (Hall & Dornan, 1990; Sitzia & Wood, 1997; Korkmaz, Büyük, & rızalar 2015; Budu et al., 2019), they contradict findings from other studies showing a clear gender bias for female patients (Keressens, Bnesing, & Andrea, 1997).

Other research done in different segments of society were analyzed, and it was revealed that in a research performed by Ünver and Ürkmez (2010), 61.4% of the participants considered nursing was a career for females. Furthermore, in a research conducted by Ünsal, Akalın, and Yılmaz (2010) to ascertain the opinions of members of various occupations (police, academics, and teachers) on male nurses, it was revealed that 85.8% believed that males could be as good as females in nursing and that more teachers believed that males could be nurses when compared to the other occupation groups (93.4%).

Kaya, Turan, and Öztürk (2011) conducted research that sought to ascertain society's perception of male nurses; 62.6% of respondents replied that nursing is a profession open to men and women. However, according to Ekinci et al.'s (2014) research, 44.7% of engineering faculty students believed nursing was a female-dominated profession, whereas 58.5% expressed a desire to receive nursing services from female nurses.

When studies conducted with health clients were examined, such as Koç and Sağlam (2010), who investigated the opinions of adult clients receiving hospital care, 60% of adult clients indicated that nursing is a gender-neutral career. According to Özbaşaran, Taşpınar, and Çakmakçı (2002), 44.4% of clients claimed that males could also be nurses. Çelik, Pasinlioğlu, Çilek, and Çelebi (2012) rendered that 53.2% of female clients (n:530) in gynecological clinics believe nursing is a female-dominated profession. On the other hand, Tezel, Balcı Akpınar, Yurttaş, and Çelebioğlu (2008), 47.8% of clients believe that the gender of nurses is irrelevant.

In this research, mothers indicated that male nurses should care for patients. Furthermore, from their point of view, nursing is a demanding profession that entails male nurse participation in the care process, and that gender prejudice should not exist in nursing. 49% of the mothers claimed that male nurses should care for male patients, 26% claimed that males should also choose nursing careers due to the difficulty of the work, and 15% answered that there should be no gender discrimination in the nursing profession.

Ekinci et al. (2014) research suggested that the most often offered response to the question "what kind of a contribution does it make for men to join the occupation of nursing?" was "they will support female nurses in things that require physical strength" (41%).

In a research conducted by Koç and Sağlam (2010), 73.8% of clients agreed that when males become nurses, there would be fewer obstacles in the occupation, and 92.5% of clients agreed that male nurses would assist their female colleagues in tasks that demand physical force as they are adept.

According to some mothers who took part in this research, nursing is a woman's work that is unsuitable for men. Ahmad and Alasad's (2007) study findings revealed that just 3.4% of mothers favored male nurses, stating that suited nursing women, male nurses may have difficulty relating with patients, and society may respond negatively to male nurses (Kocaer et al., 2004).

Koç and Sağlam (2010) reported that 55.2% of clients believed nursing was a more acceptable profession for women since it needed empathy and kindness.

Going through research conducted on clients' opinions toward requesting care from male nurses. Lodge, Mallet, Blake, and Fryatt (1997) study revealed that 28% of clients receiving gynecological services stated that it would be awkward to receive assistance from a male nurse, while Chur-Hansen (2002) research findings rendered that 47.6% of clients would feel uncomfortable with a male nurse bathing them.

Taşç (2007) claimed that 52.9% of clients believed male nurses should care for male clients and that 62% would have difficulty communicating with a male nurse if they faced any issues. Demiray, Olgun, Kaçar, and Eşer (2013) reported that while 69% of clients want to be cared for by male nurses and 76.5% believed male nurses were capable of providing care, they claimed that female clients would have difficulty communicating with male nurses when there was a problem. Tezel et al. (2008) found that most clients reported experiencing communication hurdles and feelings of embarrassment and discomfort while cared for by male nurses.

The participating mothers' statements regarding examining patients as one of the tasks of male nurses indicate that they view male physicians and male medical students as male nurses. In addition, most mothers claimed that they were aware of male nurses working in hospitals and discovered them during their visit to the hospital.

Ünsal et al. (2010) discovered statistically significant differences amongst various occupation parties and realized the existence of male nurses, men working as nurses, and men being nurses. Further, they discovered that the importance of being mindful of male nurses stems from academic and law enforcement participation.

According to Koç and Sağlam (2010), clients over the age of 67 who were married and primary school graduates, whose families lived in the city, whose incomes and expenses were equal, and who had many children believed that nursing was a male and female occupation, whereas those who lived in towns and villages believed that nursing was a female occupation.

The current study demonstrated that as mother's level of education increased, their perspectives towards male nurses grew, and they accepted male nurses more. These findings align with Çelik et al.'s (2012) research which indicated that women with poor education had less choice for male nurses. Additionally, Demiray et al. (2013) reported that illiterate and secondary school patients were more likely to choose the term "Nursing is a female-dominated career," but high school graduates were more likely to choose the statement "Men can also be nurses."

Finally, this research hopes to provide a more thorough understanding of the processes of male socialization to facilitate the projection of the image of men in society. This will require shifting sexual stereotypes: "Caregiving is not feminine-it's universal" (Hebert, 2002)

Conclusion & Implementation to Nursing

Based on the results, it was concluded that mothers had favorable attitudes toward male nurses.

As nursing has traditionally been a female-dominated profession, it is critical to understand societal views toward male nurses to increase male students enrolled in nursing schools. For citizens of society to respond to a transition, a certain amount of time must elapse.

Thus, to raise societal realization, it is proposed that the media educate the public about the efforts of male nurses.

The research examined a murky area in mothers of hospitalized children's attitudes and perspectives on care quality provided by male nurses at the medical and surgical wards of the Queen Rania Al Abdullah Hospital for Children. Although age, educational level, work status, residency, & income status, were just the significant factors of their perspectives on male nurses' care, the effect of the other variables should not be underestimated. Therefore, it is advised that male nurses' professional socialization be reinforced via the development of role models and increased public knowledge of the function of male nurses in the healthcare delivery system to foster acceptance of gender diversity in the nursing profession.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the mothers for support of the study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Financial Disclosure

The researchers met research expenses.

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